

The response of a point-absorber wave energy converter (WEC) is highly dependent on the geometry of the WEC float. Accurate characterization of WEC float hydrodynamics is therefore critical to WEC modeling and control co-design. A detailed understanding of these hydrodynamics can be obtained by isolating added mass, radiation damping, and wave excitation force as a function of oscillation frequency. These hydrodynamic parameters are commonly defined through boundary element method (BEM) simulations and experiments. BEM is often employed due to its computational efficiency, but the method relies on several assumptions including “small” amplitude motion and inviscid flow. These assumptions result in amplitude independent hydrodynamic parameters. In some cases, these approximations are appropriate, but if the float geometry and/or wave conditions result in significant viscous losses or oscillation amplitude, then BEM accuracy is reduced. To better understand where nonlinear hydrodynamics are significant, we experimentally evaluate hydrodynamic parameters for a range of float geometries operating in heave. These experimental results are analyzed to identify geometric features and experimental conditions that result in nonlinear hydrodynamics, and are compared to BEM simulations to identify discrepancies.

To experimentally determine the hydrodynamic coefficients of different geometries, forced oscillation experiments are conducted in heave over a range of oscillation frequencies and amplitudes. Added mass and radiation damping coefficients as a function of frequency are computed from the experimental data for each amplitude tested. The variation in these two hydrodynamic parameters with oscillation amplitude is used to quantify amplitude-dependent nonlinearity. Initial experiments involving forced oscillation experiments at two amplitudes have been completed for two float geometries: a scale-model of the Sandia National Laboratories “WaveBot” float, and a cylindrical float with a larger diameter cylinder attached to the bottom (i.e., a top hat shape). Both models have the same maximum diameter and draft. The experimental added mass and radiation damping coefficients for the model WaveBot are generally consistent with BEM results, but diverge at low oscillation frequencies. Similar agreement is observed for added mass with the “top hat” shape, but damping is consistently underpredicted by simulation, possibly due to viscous forces. Additionally, the radiation damping coefficient exhibits stronger amplitude dependence for the hat-shaped model than the WaveBot. Further experiments involve higher amplitude oscillations, additional oscillation frequencies, and additional float geometries. The results from these experiments provide guidance on geometries and/or motion that result in nonlinear hydrodynamics and are therefore not accurately modeled by BEM.



WaveBot Model



Top Hat Model